

D1.8 Second Update DMP

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Abstract	The CRAFT-OA Data Management Plan provides information about data reused or produced in the project. The document presents the origin of the data, the methods of their processing, use and storage, as well as the actions taken to make them comply with FAIR principles.

Version and Revision History

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

D	Deliverable
DDH	Diamond Discovery Hub
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOC	Legacy Word Document
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IPSPs	Institutional Publishing Service Providers
IPTPs	Institutional Publishing Technology Providers
JMEF	Journal Metadata Exchange Format
M	Milestone
maDMP	machine actionable Data Management Plan
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

OJS	Open Journal Systems
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
RDA JSON	Research. Data Alliance JavaScript Object Notation
T	Task
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 1.8 “Second Update DMP” focuses on describing the data generated and reused during project activities of the CRAFT-OA project, according to good scientific practice and efforts in support of Open Science and transparency inherent in any research project. Because of the variety, complexity, and variability of the data that can be associated with the project, this document is crucial for describing the correct handling of resources throughout the lifespan of the project and will remain essential after the project has ended. D1.8 is a document based on the original CRAFT-OA project DMP (D1.2) together with the First Update DMP (D1.7), but updated with information acquired during the last 18 months of the project. D1.8 is the final version of the CRAFT-OA Data Management Plan (DMP).

The Deliverable is divided into three sections, which together provide a complete overview of data management in the CRAFT-OA project:

- The “Method” section contains information on what methods and tools have been chosen to prepare descriptions of the datasets provided in each Work Package (WP). This section also contains information on the changes made after the first and second DMP updates.
- The “General data description” section provides a general overview of the project data, which is the basis for understanding the specifics of the project and an introduction to the detailed part.
- The “CRAFT-OA DMP datasets” section is the main element of the DMP. This is the content exported from the Argos¹ online tool and contains detailed information for each dataset in a format based on the guidelines of the European Commission (EC).

By its nature, the DMP should be treated as a living document that is subject to constant review, revision and amendment. This document is the final version produced at the end of the project. All versions of DMP are publicly available on the Argos² platform as well as in CRAFT-OA’s community in the Zenodo³ repository.

¹ About Argos: <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/about/how-it-works.html>

² CRAFT-OA DMP in Argos available at: <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/overview/public/3a7172b2-a22d-45ad-9a15-6a445244ba72>

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/craft-oa/>

2 METHOD

In large-scale projects, such as CRAFT-OA, it is important to adopt an adequate strategy when preparing the Data Management Plan (DMP). With large and diverse amounts of data, this document can become hard to create, and the need to control variability by introducing subsequent versions can cause further difficulties. This section presents the solutions that have been selected to overcome these difficulties and produce a qualitative DMP in line with the European Commission's (EC)⁴ guidelines.

2.1 Data Management Plan requirements

It is important to specify what scope the DMP should cover. Any research data that were generated or reused during the project were included in the plan. This includes all research data, survey responses, workshop records, project documentation, written project outcomes (such as Deliverables), personal data, software developed, etc. The described output data are not limited in terms of formats, so it can be textual, numerical, graphical, video or audio.

The main rule during the creation of the DMP was to achieve compliance with the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse (FAIR) data principles⁵, legal requirements (e.g. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)) and the guidelines of the EC. The last section of this document contains detailed information on how data management in the project corresponds to the assumptions that data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable as much as possible. The data descriptions also include information about data security and potential ethical issues (if necessary).

2.2 Machine actionable Data Management Plan

In order to simplify the process of creating a DMP and standardise the information produced in this way, it was decided to look for a tool that would enable it. The answer to this type of need is a machine actionable DMP (maDMP) which is an extension of the standard DMP approach⁶.

The advantage of the tools supporting this type of solution is the adaptation of this previously only human-readable document to the technological requirements of modern data exchange practices. Adapting the data description structure in such a way that it is possible to create files that can be easily processed by computers significantly improves interoperability, sharing and reuse of information contained in the document. Relying on machine actionable DMPs allows integration of standardised information, e.g. employing persistent identifiers, and ensures the unification of at least part of the information.

⁴ Information on the structure and content of the DMP is available, for example, in the Data management plan (HE) file available in the Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Reference Documents: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents>

⁵ Wilkinson et al. (2016).

⁶ More information: Miksa et al. (2020), Simms et al. (2017).

2.3 Tool

The Argos platform, an online service developed by Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE)⁷ and EUDAT⁸ that can be used to create a maDMP and manage its subsequent versions, was selected for the creation of the CRAFT-OA DMP. It allows the simultaneous collaboration of many users while working on one DMP. Working with Argos consists of adding descriptions of datasets using simple questionnaires based on templates adapted to the requirements of individual projects. The tool also allows exporting the finished DMP in Portable Document Format (PDF), Legacy Word Document (DOC), Extensible Markup Language (XML) and Research Data Alliance JavaScript Object Notation (RDA JSON⁹) formats. It is possible to quickly deposit a document in the Zenodo repository and get a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Argos itself is a platform that allows users to search and view DMPs marked as public.

2.4 Workflow

The preparation of the data descriptions was based on the participation of the leaders of the individual WPs. Leaders entered dataset information into Argos using available questionnaires using the Horizon Europe template (based on EC guidelines). WP leads used their knowledge of the tasks outlined in their work packages to present the data details as reliably as possible. After preparing the datasets, the descriptions were additionally verified. The result is information that represents the management of data at the current project stage within individual WPs.

As far as possible, data of similar type, structure, origin and characterised by similar use and storage were grouped within single datasets to maintain a reasonable level of fragmentation of information.

Not all possible fields of the questionnaires were filled in in all cases, depending on the specificity of the described resources, some fields were omitted if they were not required. As the project activities progressed, additional datasets were added and refined. All changes were incorporated into the DMP in Argos.

2.5 First update

After 18 months of the project, the original content of the DMP was reviewed to ensure that its structure and the information contained therein were clear and possibly well reflected in the approach to the data produced by the project.

When analysing the existing structure of the data descriptions in the DMP, the project team concluded that it was too broad and thus blurring the picture for potential audiences. The

⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu>

⁸ <https://www.eudat.eu>

⁹ RDA JSON is a format designed according to Research Data Alliance (<https://www.rd-alliance.org>) guidelines to facilitate the exchange of information by systems working with machine-actionable data management plans. For more information go to <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard/tree/master>

previous approach was based on descriptions of data created in individual WPs, which made the information difficult to manage and, due to recurring types of resources across WPs, led to redundant and repetitive descriptions.

It was decided to create new descriptions, more focused on the similarity of certain groups of data and the method of storing and sharing them. The information contained in the 14 existing descriptions was analysed and combined into groups with similar characteristics. This resulted in 7 descriptions of the data handled in the project:

- Project documentation
- Personal and contact data
- Analyses, requirements, recommendations, technical documentations, workflows
- Workshop and training materials
- Survey data
- Software
- Metadata

Following the changes to the Argos software, the descriptions have been made available to the WP leaders for review and to make the necessary changes and updates.

According to the project team, the new, simplified structure of the DMP will allow for better management of project data and will increase transparency of CRAFT-OA towards its users.

2.6 Second update

After 36 months of the project, the DMP was reviewed for the final time to verify its consistency with the current state of data production and management within the project. The review focused primarily on confirming the accuracy and completeness of the information already included, as the structure and general approach established in the previous update proved effective and sufficient for the project's needs.

Only minor, cosmetic adjustments were introduced, mainly concerning wording and clarification of certain descriptions. The project team verified the datasets' structure and confirmed that the modifications introduced in the previous update had been fully implemented and remained valid. No new datasets or substantial changes in data handling procedures were identified.

The final version of the DMP thus reflects the stable and mature state of the project's data management practices, ensuring consistency, transparency, and long-term usability of the data produced within the CRAFT-OA project.

3 GENERAL DATA DESCRIPTION

A whole range of data of different types was produced during the project. Although each WP has individual specificities of the tasks assigned in the project, some types of material are common concerning the outputs that WPs generate. The data envisaged at an early stage of the project can be divided into certain groups based on their type, origin or expected handling during the project. The groups specified at this point are:

- **Coordination and reporting materials** – collaboratively produced materials for coordinating activities, such as notes from project meetings, are primarily maintained in Confluence¹⁰. Additional working documents may be created in Google Documents format and saved and stored on institutional servers e.g. as Word files or similar. For all reports and deliverables, the target format is PDF. Documents whose content permits this will be made public under Open Access (OA) rules.
- **Analyses, requirements, recommendations, etc.** – all qualitative project documentation including analyses, recommendations or guidelines that have been produced during the project, whether intended to be made public (e.g. in the form of deliverables) or so produced only for the project activities. The storage method is Google Drive project space in Google Docs, Google Sheets or similar formats. Documents that were planned to be made available to users in advance, or those that have gained this status by their substantive content value, were made public in Zenodo repository under OA rules.
- **Survey and training materials** – in some WPs, user needs research was carried out, which involved obtaining personal information where necessary. All such datasets were anonymised when required and processed in accordance with GDPR principles. All training materials (e.g. presentations, videos) were prepared in a way that maximised their content value and ensured their accessibility and reusability. Some of the training materials were made publicly available through platforms such as GitBook¹¹, while video content was shared via YouTube (channels: OPERAS Research Infrastructure, OpenAIRE_eu, and DIAMAS Project) or the TIB AV-Portal¹².
- **Software data** – tasks which create or extend the functionalities for the publishing platforms produced output in the form of software code (e.g. Open Journal Systems [OJS] plugins mostly written in PHP language). Source code was treated with due regard to the rules of the open-source community and stored in one of the leading developer platforms – GitHub. Plugins for OJS prepared in the project were included in the OJS V3.5 release.
- **Metadata of scholarly records** – some of the project tasks, such as the development of the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH), involved processing a large number of metadata records for enrichment purposes. Data was ingested into the DDH via spreadsheet uploads or the JMEF OJS plugin.¹³ Subsequently, the records were

¹⁰ Confluence – an online collaborative workspace used for creating, sharing and managing documentation within teams. <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>

¹¹ GitBook is an online platform for creating, hosting, and sharing structured documentation, manuals, and training materials in a collaborative way. <https://www.gitbook.com/>

¹² <https://av.tib.eu/>

¹³ <https://ddh.diamas.org/docs/become-a-trusted-source/>

converted into standardised formats, including Dublin Core and the Journal Metadata Exchange Format (JMEF), and made available for harvesting through the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) protocol¹⁴.

In all the groups mentioned above, where possible, efforts were made to fully integrate with the FAIR principles. All personal data processed in the course of the project were handled in compliance with the GDPR. Details of the datasets produced by each WP are provided in the next section (4 CRAFT-OA DMP datasets).

¹⁴ <https://ddh.diamas.org/docs/oai-api-documentation/>

4 CRAFT-OA DMP DATASETS

This section contains dataset descriptions exported from Argos. Each of the subsections (4.x) corresponds to one dataset. Within one dataset, below the words “Dataset Description”, there are numbered questions and answers corresponding to the individual questions in the Argos questionnaire template.

The datasets below represent Version 2 of the CRAFT-OA DMP in Argos. The template used to create dataset descriptions in Argos is Horizon Europe template¹⁵. For all the questions provided by the template read Appendix 1. Argos Horizon Europe template – list of questions.

The information included in the DMP, based on the ARGOS template, is as complete as possible. However, certain sections may be partially completed or omitted where they were not applicable to the project or where the required information could not be reasonably obtained. In addition, some exported elements may appear slightly ambiguous when taken out of the ARGOS interface context; therefore, brief clarifications have occasionally been added in square brackets.

4.1 Project documentation

Overview

This dataset contains internal project documentation and documents related to communication between project teams. It includes any documents produced in any WP to coordinate work on tasks (e.g. rolling minutes, internal technical documentation), outputs of the project (deliverables, reports, etc. describing the internal functioning of the project, which cannot be regarded as information available to the public.) as well as other data created or collected for internal management.

1. Summary

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix]

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

¹⁵ The Horizon Europe template that was used for the CRAFT-OA DMP is a questionnaire template prepared by the Argos platform administrators. It is intended to comply as widely as possible with the EC guidelines for DMPs of projects participating in the Horizon Europe programme.

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New [The option in the selection list indicates the generation of new data.]

1.1.5 What is its format?

Google Document Link File, .doc/.docx, .pdf

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

<1GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix]

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed [The data is not supposed to be shared - status "Closed" selected.]

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

The documents described are for internal project management only. Some project outputs (deliverables) are intended for internal purposes and shared only with the consortium and the European Commission.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 [value]

Euro [currency]

Storage [RDM activity]

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4.2 Personal and contact data

Overview

This dataset includes personal data collected for project management as well as internal and external communication purposes from all WPs. It contains mail addresses, names, affiliations, post addresses, sociodemographic data, mailing lists, event registration, sign-ups for newsletters, chat logs, meeting recordings, device IDs, location, and IP addresses. Collected data was processed and stored protected enough to comply with GDPR requirements.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix]

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New [The option in the selection list indicates the generation of new data.]

Data used for management purposes were filled in and shared with the Coordinator by the responsible project or work package leader for the project members from their partner institutions at the beginning of the project via an Admin Sheet and were shared for project members who joined later usually by e-mail.

In addition to the personal data, most of which was newly collected in the course of the project, the contact details from the DIAMAS project¹⁶ of Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) and Institutional Publishing Technology Providers (IPTPs) were used in selected cases, e. g. for the distribution of the survey in WP4. As participants from the DIAMAS survey, they had explicitly consented to further contact and inclusion in the IPTP/IPSP registries¹⁷. The use and processing of the reused data was also performed in a GDPR-compliant way.

¹⁶ <https://diamasproject.eu/>

¹⁷ <https://registry.diamas.org/>

1.1.5 What is its format?

Google Document Link File, .csv, .doc/.docx, .pdf, .jpeg/.jpg/.jpg2, .png, .wav, .mp3, .mp4, .html, .css

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

10 - 12 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

Personal data was collected to manage the project and is stored according to the guidelines from the European Commission only as long as necessary to enable the Coordinator and the consortium members to document the project processes and results, e. g. in the context of possible audits. Additionally, the data was used to inform e.g. the project members and external persons about project results, meetings and events after their consent. According to GDPR, it is possible for project members and externals to withdraw consent from data storage at any time. The personal data is stored on institutional, access-protected servers with a backup routine, to which only a limited number of people have access.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix]

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers [DOI]
- Researchers identifiers [ORCID]
- Organizations identifiers [ROR]

In case a recording of an event or any communication output were published, all outputs appeared in the CRAFT-OA Zenodo Community and thereby have a DOI, the authors of and contributors to the project results like deliverables were identified as far as possible via ORCID.

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

yes, such as authors (possibly ORCID), title, DOI, description, date, keywords

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

No

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

At least for Zenodo publications.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

zenodo.org

not all data will be published in this repository but a part of it

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

DOI

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Closed

Mailing lists etc. for management purposes were only shared with the coordination and communication task force. Recordings were made public, with the approval of the participants.

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset / output?

Personal data is under special protection and is only shared publicly with the consent of the project members or after external participants have given their approval.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

The personal data of the project will only be stored (as long as the consent of the person is not withdrawn before) as long as necessary following the guidelines of the EC and the requirements of the partner institutions.

Only colleagues granted access by the coordination team can access the personal data for management purposes. This data is stored on institutional servers with backup routines and can be accessed using their individual institutional login.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

The storage of basic personal data for logins to platforms or services will be necessary by the organizations that enable the sustainable availability of the content and services after the project has ended. Users have the possibility to delete their data at any time. Project results, like deliverables and the data contained, will be preserved by the Zenodo repository¹⁸. The personal data of the project will only be stored (as long as the consent of the person is not withdrawn before) as long as necessary following the guidelines of the EC and the requirements of the partner institutions to enable possible audits after the project has ended.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

No

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

The personal data for management processes is under current control and will be cleaned, (re-)structured and supplemented if necessary by the coordination team.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 [value]

Euro [currency]

Storage [RDM activity]

¹⁸ <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Use of institution infrastructure

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Other

Personal data is only used and available project-internally. Sociodemographic data concerning the website were collected via a Matomo plug-in, meaning they are GDPR-compliant. In case events were recorded, participants received a legal disclaimer informing them about their rights and could choose to attend the event without being recorded. X (Twitter) Analytics, a third-party service, was used to collect data for KPIs from X (Twitter). Personal data was not shared via Twitter except with the consent of the person. All mailing lists were hosted via the partner coordinating the project, the University of Göttingen and the website is hosted by the University of Torino. The personal data for management purposes were stored on institutional servers with restricted access and with backup routines, to avoid loss of data.

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Personal data for management purposes will only be stored as long as necessary according to the guidelines of the European Commission and the institutional regulations, e.g. of the University of Göttingen as coordinator, to enable transparent documentation of the project within possible audits during and after the project.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

Yes

Personal data is collected.

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

Yes

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4.3 Analyses, requirements, recommendations, technical documentations, workflows

Overview

This dataset contains all project outputs such as analyses, requirements, recommendations, technical documentations, workflows etc. intended to be made available to users for further use.

It contains, for example, the results of the following Work Packages:

WP2: D2.2 Reusable curriculum for upskilling trainings; D2.3 Technical Gap Analysis & High-level Community Transition Plans

WP3: D3.1 Report on standards for best publishing practices and basic technical standards, inspired by the FAIR principles; D3.2 Report on challenges and help measures faced by OA journals and platforms

WP4: T4.4 – deployment and upgrading toolkits and recommendations for OJS and Lodel, based on a requirement survey.

WP5: 1) T5.1 – texts and tables documenting the technical requirements and recommendations of citation indexes and aggregators. 2) T5.2 – the dataset includes results of an analysis of status quo, documentation for technical requirements, and design of the workflows of the Visibility Pathfinder, a tool that will allow journals to self-assess their current level of visibility and provide feedback on how to improve it via the CRAFT-OA DDH, including the technical description of its integration within existing publishing systems (e.g. OJS) and a set of visuals to indicate the level of compliance to the journal users.

WP6: Recommendation for publishers for handling research supporting data; Federated Trust and Identity (T&I) technical requirements, architecture and best practices

WP7: Toolkit for IPTP Network; Institutional publishing technical living handbook

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Workflows [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Workflows” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix]

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New [The option in the selection list indicates the generation of new data.]

For task T5.1: The dataset consists of a collection of freely available public information about technical requirements for publications referencing.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

Around 1 GB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

For task T5.1: The dataset was used for: 1) informing the target group (diamond publishers) about the aggregators' technical requirements; 2) guiding the WP members in building the service that will help reference the publications on various service providers' platforms.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry
- Other

For WP3: Publishing platforms, publishers, and stand-alone Diamond OA journals

For task T5.1: The dataset targets mainly two groups within the research community: the diamond publishers, and the partners involved in the building of support services for the diamond publishers.

2.1 Publications

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/pkp>, <https://github.com/OpenEdition/lodel>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers [DOI]
- Projects identifiers [Cordis]

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

For task T5.1: The final deliverable uses Dublin Core metadata in Zenodo services.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo CRAFT-OA Community

<https://zenodo.org/communities/craft-oa/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Assigns PIDs
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

For task T5.1: Yes, to the file (textual, spreadsheets, presentation, etc.)

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

CRAFT-OA: Analyses, requirements, recommendations, technical documentations, workflows

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

Couldn't find it? Insert it manually

For task T5.1: Dublin Core in Zenodo services.

3.3.7 Does the described dataset / output provide qualified references with other outputs?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

For task T5.1: Information sources for the establishment of the dataset were explicitly mentioned and referenced.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 [value]

Euro [currency]

- Storage [RDM activity]
- Archiving [RDM activity]
- Re-use [RDM activity]
- Security [RDM activity]

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

- Infrastructure Grant
- Other

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

Public versions of the deliverables are openly accessible, working documents are stored separately and accessible only to the partners of the project upon identification.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4.4 Workshop and training materials

Overview

This dataset includes workshop and training materials produced in Work Packages 2, 3, 4 and 7.

Examples of elements of this dataset:

WP2: Training and Engagement Materials Package

WP3: Training materials on implementing technical standards and self-assessment toolkit

WP4: Part of the data created in task T4.4 include online workshops in the form of “Meet the Experts” video presentations aimed at journal managers and technical staff.

WP7: Materials related to the outreach, dissemination and engagement activities, e.g. the recordings of the cross-project webinars organised in collaboration with the DIAMAS and PALOMERA project¹⁹ or the “Shaping Diamond OA: Criteria for Journals”²⁰ webinar held together with the DIAMAS project.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix]

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New [The option in the selection list indicates the generation of new data]

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

20MB

¹⁹ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>

²⁰ Shaping Diamond OA: Criteria for Journals, 16 May 2024, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TpGbvrHT8VI>

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

To share information

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Research communities
- Industry
- Other

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/pkp>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Data identifiers [DOI]

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

Registry/Catalogue

3.2 Making data and other outputs openly accessible

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is an EC-co-funded, repository, for publications and data. A DOI is automatically assigned to all items and Zenodo allows for versioning. Both publications and research data can be published and Zenodo provides means to link them. Data is stored in the CERN cloud infrastructure. Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon Europe and OpenAIRE.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 [value]

Euro [currency]

- Storage [RDM activity]
- Archiving [RDM activity]

Direct cost [This was selected from the two available options—direct cost and indirect cost]

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the cost because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix.]

5 Security

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data storage

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4.5 Survey data

Overview

This dataset contains data obtained through surveys carried out during the project in Work Packages 3, 4 and 7. These include surveys targeting institutional IT departments and surveys targeting editorial staff of scholarly journals.

An additional set of data is a large extent of semi-structured interviews provided by the University of Bern with platform service providers and journal editors.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New [The option in the selection list indicates the generation of new data.]

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other

1.1.5 What is its format?

For University of Bern data:

- Questionnaire templates (PDF)
- Audio files interviews (MP4)
- Interview transcriptions (PDF)
- Reports (PDF)
- Consent forms (Word, PDF)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

The data volume does not exceed 1 GB.

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions

For University of Bern data:

The data are essentially interviews conducted with 11 platform operators and journal editors.

The qualitative study, conducted with semi-structured interviews, provides information on what platform service providers and journal editors think needs to be improved to make Diamond-OA publishing more sustainable and easier. This information was incorporated into the CRAFT-OA project.

The questionnaires and transcriptions of the interviews in anonymized form have been made publicly available for reuse. They can be used for work in the field of information science and scholarly communications or start-ups or reorganizations of platforms and journals.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Industry
- Other

For University of Bern data: The questionnaires and transcriptions of the interviews in anonymized form have been made publicly available for reuse. They can be used for work in the field of information science and scholarly communications or start-ups or reorganizations of platforms and journals.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

Yes

<https://github.com/pkp/>

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers [DOI]
- Researchers identifiers [ORCID]
- Organizations identifiers [ROR]

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

All data are published on Zenodo. Zenodo is an EC-co-funded, repository, for publications and data. A DOI is automatically assigned to all items and Zenodo allows for versioning. Both publications and research data can be published and Zenodo provides means to link them. Data is stored in the CERN cloud infrastructure. Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon Europe and OpenAIRE.

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

For University of Bern data: The DataCite Metadata Schema is used as the standard metadata schema for all published data.

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Linked Open Data

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

For University of Bern data: All results published on Zenodo or BORIS are provided with search keywords together with their metadata. Keywords for open data were selected wherever possible from controlled vocabularies that were suitable for the specific type of data. Where no suitable vocabularies were available free-form keywords were used.

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

Yes, metadata (CC0) is freely accessible via open interfaces.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is an EC-co-funded, repository, for publications and data. A DOI is automatically assigned to all items and Zenodo allows for versioning. Both publications and research data can be published and Zenodo provides means to link them. Data is stored in the CERN cloud infrastructure. Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon Europe and OpenAIRE.

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

A DOI is automatically assigned to all items and Zenodo allows for versioning. Both publications and research data can be published and Zenodo provides means to link them. Data is stored in the CERN cloud infrastructure. Zenodo is compliant with the open data requirements of Horizon Europe and OpenAIRE.

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open [Selected from the options “Open,” “Shared,” and “Closed,” this choice best reflects the nature of the dataset/output.]

For University of Bern data: The questionnaire templates, the anonymized transcriptions, and the report are publicly available. The individual consent forms and the audio files will not be made publicly available for privacy reasons. The audio files and the not anonymized transcriptions are stored on a local drive at the University of Bern and will be deleted after the end of the project.

For other surveys: The surveys sought consent for data sharing.

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

For University of Bern data: The questionnaire templates, the anonymized transcriptions, and the report are publicly available. The individual consent forms and the audio files will not be made publicly available for privacy reasons. The audio files and the not anonymized transcriptions are stored in the campus storage of the University of Bern and deleted after the end of the project.

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset / output will be made accessible for

According to Zenodo’s general policies (<http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>), “items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.”

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

No

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

Yes

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 What reusability and / or reproducibility methods are followed?

README files

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

For University of Bern data: A README file with the information relevant to the project was published together with the data. For this purpose, the following template was adapted:

https://www.ub.unibe.ch/unibe/portal/unibiblio/content/e6304/e583799/e573822/e1085861/e1085890/e1085891/pane1085902/e1198324/Readme_Template_EN_v2_20220511_eng.txt

The data is published under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC-BY 4.0) licence.

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

50 [value]

Swiss Franc [currency]

Storage [RDM activity]

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the cost because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix.]

5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Passwords

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

For University of Bern data: The data is stored on servers managed by the IT of the University of Bern. Only the project staff involved have access to the data. Access is regulated by password protection. The data on the university servers are automatically backed up daily. Questionnaire templates for the interviews will be stored on Microsoft OneDrive, provided by the University of Bern. The servers are located and managed in Switzerland. Due to the non-sensitive nature of the templates, this should not pose a security risk.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

No

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Yes

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?

Anonymising data where necessary

For University of Bern data: A consent form is obtained from all interview partners. Data will only be published in anonymised form and identifying data (audio files) will be deleted.

We let a person from the project team check transcription and anonymization.

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4.6 Software

Overview

This dataset includes all of the software components developed in Work Packages 4, 5 and 6.

Examples of components being developed in individual WPs:

WP4: Tasks T4.1, T4.2 and T4.3 contribute to the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) applications (Open Journal Systems (OJS), Open Monograph Press (OMP), Open Preprint Systems, PKP shared library, PKP plugins) and develop independent plugins for PKP applications and Lodel. The contributions to the PKP applications are merged into the PKP repositories in Github and will not be maintained separately. Plugins developed in the project have been released on Github.

WP5: OJS plugin for the visibility pathfinder ready as MVP; Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH).

WP6: OJS connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph; OJS plugin for the EOSC Interoperability Framework on Research Product Publishing; OJS plugins for integrating feedback from EOSC catalogue; OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard Service.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Software

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New [The option in the selection list indicates the generation of new data.]

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “other” best reflects the nature of the output because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix.]

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

20MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To develop a product
- To improve a product

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Industry
- Other

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.2 Datasets

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

Other [URL]

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

No

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

GitHub

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

No

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open [Selected from the options “Open,” “Shared,” and “Closed,” this choice best reflects the nature of the dataset/output.]

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset / output will be accessed during and after the project ends

Publicly available on Github during and after the project.

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

No

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

No

3.3.4 Will you provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

No

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

GNU General Public License 3.0

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 [value]

Euro [currency]

- Storage [RDM activity]
- Archiving [RDM activity]

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Collaboration with other Projects [Selected from the list of options—Use of national infrastructure, Use of institution infrastructure, Infrastructure Grant, Collaboration with other Projects, and Other—this choice best reflects the way the cost will be covered.]

5.1 Data Security

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset / output in the long term?

Contributions to the PKP applications will be maintained/preserved by the PKP community.

How to maintain the developed plugins after the project runtime will be the responsibility in CRAFT-OA WP7.

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

6.1.3 Does the described dataset / output contain personal data?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

4.7 Metadata

Overview

This dataset contains all metadata produced and processed during the project.

WP5: T5.3 The Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) increases the visibility of diamond journals on a series of major platforms and aggregators. To that end, it collects, harmonizes, enriches, and disseminates metadata of diamond OA journals. The DDH dataset comprises metadata of journals and articles, some components of the OpenAIRE Graph, and other sets of data.

The OpenAIRE Graph Dump was used to reuse existing metadata for diamond OA journals and related research outputs. This enabled the enrichment and contextualization of the dataset by leveraging a large, openly available collection of scholarly metadata linking articles, datasets, software, organisations, funders, and projects.

Dataset Description

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

Re-used

Metadata in the Diamond Discovery Hub and from OpenAIRE Graph will be re-used and redesigned for new purposes.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Derived or compiled

1.1.6. What is its expected size?

The current size: 170 MB, annual data growth: around 50 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

- To improve a product
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

For task T5.3: Existing publishing platforms and services generating standard metadata for their publications.

The OpenAIRE Graph Dump was used to reuse existing metadata for diamond OA journals and related research outputs.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public
- Industry
- Other

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers
- National identifiers
- Other

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Structural
- Reference

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

Yes

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

0 [value]

Euro [currency]

Storage [RDM activity]

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other [This choice follows from the available options in the selection list, where “Other” best reflects the nature of the cost because none of the predefined categories apply, as detailed in the appendix.]

5.1 Data Security

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data access
- Data sharing

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

Unknown

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

5 REFERENCES

All references and websites mentioned in the document were last checked for availability on 03.11.2025.

5.1 List of References

Miksa, T.; Walk, P. & Neish, P. (2020). RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>

Simms, S.; Jones, S.; Mietchen, D. & Miksa, T. (2017). Machine-actionable data management plans (maDMPs). *Research Ideas and Outcomes* 3: e13086. <https://doi.org/10.3897/rio.3.e13086>

Wilkinson, M. D. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3: 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

5.2 List of Websites

<http://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

<https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/overview/public/3a7172b2-a22d-45ad-9a15-6a445244ba72>

<https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/about/how-it-works.html>

<https://av.tib.eu/>

<https://commission.europa.eu>

<https://ddh.diamas.org/docs/become-a-trusted-source/>

<https://ddh.diamas.org/docs/oai-api-documentation/>

<https://diamasproject.eu/>

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/reference-documents>

<https://github.com/OpenEdition/lodel>

<https://github.com/pkp>

<https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard/tree/master>

<https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/>

<https://registry.diamas.org/>

<https://schema.datacite.org/>

<https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>

<https://www.eudat.eu>

<https://www.gitbook.com/>

<https://www.openaire.eu>

<https://www.rd-alliance.org>

[https://www.ub.unibe.ch/unibe/portal/unibiblio/content/e6304/e583799/e573822/e1085861/e1085890/e1085891/pane1085902/e1198324/Readme Template EN v2 20220511 eng.txt](https://www.ub.unibe.ch/unibe/portal/unibiblio/content/e6304/e583799/e573822/e1085861/e1085890/e1085891/pane1085902/e1198324/Readme%20Template%20EN%20v2%2020220511%20eng.txt)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TpGbvrHT8VI>

<https://zenodo.org/communities/craft-oa/>

APPENDIX 1. ARGOS HORIZON EUROPE TEMPLATE – LIST OF QUESTIONS

*Options available for selection are given in square brackets.

1. SUMMARY

1.1. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?
[Research Data, Software, Workflows, Protocols, Models, Other]

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?
[Physical, Digital, Other]

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?
[New, Re-used]

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?
[Sample or specimen Data, Observational, Experimental, Simulation, Derived or compiled, Reference or canonical, Other]

1.1.5 What is its format?

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?
[To obtain information, To share information, To keep on record, To make informed decisions, To develop a product, To improve a product, To combine with other data, Other]

1.1.8 What is its origin/provenance?

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?
[Researchers, Research communities, Decision makers, Education, Economy, The public, Industry, Other]

2. LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1. PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?
[Yes, No]

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?
[Yes, No]

2.2. DATASETS

2.2.1 Does the described output use or support any published dataset?

[Yes, No]

2.3. SOFTWARE

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

[Yes, No]

3. FAIR PRACTICES

3.1. MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1. MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset/output?

[Data identifiers, Researchers identifiers, Organizations identifiers, Projects identifiers, National identifiers, Other, None]

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset/output?

[Yes, No]

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

[Descriptive, Administrative, Structural, Reference, Statistical, Legal, Other]

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

[Yes, No]

3.1.1.5 Please provide URL/Description of used vocabularies

3.1.1.6. Are the metadata searchable?

[Yes, No]

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

[Registry/Catalogue, Metadata repository, Linked Open Data, Digital Asset Management, Content Management System, Web-GIS, Other]

4.1.3.1.1.8. Are keywords provided in the metadata?

[Yes, No]

4.1.3.1.1.9. Are metadata harvestable?

[Yes, No]

3.2. MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1. REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset/output be deposited?

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

[Yes, No]

3.2.1.4 Add appropriate arrangements made with the repository(ies) where the described dataset will be deposited

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets/outputs with persistent identifiers?

[Yes, No]

3.2.1.6 Does the repository(ies) resolve the identifiers to a digital object?

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

[Yes, No, Unknown]

3.2.2. DATA

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset/output title?

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset/output shared?

[Open, Shared, Closed]

3.2.2.3 What is the reason of limiting access to the dataset/output?

3.2.2.4 If an embargo applies, please specify when the dataset/output will be made available.

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset/output?

[Yes, No]

3.2.2.6 Please provide information about the method(s) needed to access the dataset/output.

3.2.2.7 Please provide information about the tools needed to access the dataset/output.

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset/output supported by a data access committee?

[Yes, No]

3.2.2.9 Please specify how the dataset/output will be accessed during and after the project ends

3.2.2.10 Please specify how long after the project has ended the dataset/output will be made accessible for

3.2.3. METADATA

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset/output can not be openly shared?

[Yes, No]

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset/output?

[Yes, No]

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset/output is no longer available?

[Yes, No]

3.3. MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

[Yes, No]

3.3.2 If you created the vocabulary, where can it be found?

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

[Yes, No]

3.3.5 What is the methodology followed?

3.3.6 What community-endorsed interoperability best practices are followed?

3.3.7 Does the described dataset/output provide qualified references with other outputs?

[Yes, No]

3.4. INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset/output?

3.4.2 What reusability and/or reproducibility methods are followed?

[Readme files, Codebooks, Data cleaning, Analyses, Variable definitions, Units of measurement, Negative results sharing, Other]

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset/output in the public domain?

[Yes, No]

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

[Yes, No]

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

[Yes, No]

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

[Set up of scientific and technical committee, Use of tools for automatic checks, Data conform to format specification, Consistency verified with data models and standards, Not available, Other]

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?
[RDM activities served: Storage, Archiving, Re-use, Security, Other]
[Direct costs, Indirect costs]

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?
[Use of national infrastructure, Use of institution infrastructure, Infrastructure grant, Collaboration with other projects, Other]

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

5. SECURITY

5.1. DATA SECURITY

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?
[Encryption, IRB protocol, Firewall, Passwords, Hash functions, Other]

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?
[Data access, Data storage, Data transmission, Data recovery, Data sharing, Other]

5.1.3 How will you preserve the described dataset/output in the long term?

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1. ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset/output?
[Yes, No, Unknown]

6.1.2 Does the described dataset/output contain sensitive information?
[Yes, No, Unknown]

6.1.3 Does the described dataset/output contain personal data?
[Yes, No, Unknown]

6.1.4 What are the methods used for processing and accessing sensitive/personal information?
[Anonymising data when necessary, Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms, Data accompanied by informed consent statements, Privacy policies, National laws, Not available, Other]

7. OTHER ISSUES

7.1. OTHER

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?
[Yes, No]

7.1.2 Documentation of other procedures